

Appendix A: Optimized geometries and calculated BE values

Geometry optimization of the ASW clusters and the BE values estimation of the 7 radicals are performed using DFT- ω B97X-D/6-311+G(d,p) level theory as stated in Section 2 of the original published manuscript.

Table A.1. Optimized geometries of 9 different ASW [H₂O]₂₀ clusters.

ASW [H ₂ O] ₂₀ clusters	<i>d</i> -H binding sites available	Optimized energy* (Hartrees)	Relative energy [Eref.= ASW(1)] (Kelvin)	Optimized [H ₂ O] ₂₀ cluster structures
ASW(1)	7	-1528.510023	0	
ASW(2)	7	-1528.499694	3262	
ASW(3)	9	-1528.505233	1513	
ASW(4)	10	-1528.494038	5048	

Table A.1. continued.

ASW[H ₂ O] ₂₀ clusters	<i>d</i> -H binding sites available	Optimized energy* (Hartrees)	Relative energy [Eref.= ASW(1)] (Kelvin)	Optimized [H ₂ O] ₂₀ cluster structures
ASW(5)	8	-1528.499406	3353	
ASW(6)	9	-1528.494265	4976	
ASW(7)	8	-1528.508844	372	
ASW(8)	9	-1528.503436	2080	
ASW(9)	8	-1528.500329	3061	

Notes. The optimized ASW [H₂O]₂₀ cluster structures are prepared using Chemcraft Version 1.8, build 682 (Zhurko 2005). Red and white balls are oxygen and hydrogen atoms, respectively.

* Optimized energy values correspond to the ZPE-corrected electronic energy in Hartree.

The $-ve$ sign indicates the stability of the structure; the larger it is, the more stable the optimized geometry.

Table A.2. Calculated BE values for OH radicals considering 9 different ASW [H₂O]₂₀ clusters.

<i>d</i> -H binding sites	BE values (Kelvin)		Highest BE value (Kelvin)	
	-BSSE	+BSSE	-BSSE	+BSSE
ASW(1)				
1	2465	2162		
2	2955	2674		
3	1880	1500	3990	3643
4	3125	2816		
5	3990	3643	(S.F. $\approx$ 1.188)	$\approx$ 1.177
6	3116	2793		
7	1662	1452		
ASW(2)				
1	1709	1495		
2	1498	1265		
3	2887	2553		
4	4734	4296	4734	4296
5	2957	2630		
6	3456	3130		
7	4349	3914		
ASW(3)				
1	3410	3063		
2	3435	2931		
3	2939	2640		
4	1683	1456		
5	5580	5028	5580	5028
6	3906	3482		
7	1758	1532		
8	3346	2999		
9	4492	4080		
ASW(4)				
1	3676	3331		
2	3948	3481		
3	3219	2888		
4	2964	2508		
5	1799	1573	4719	4261
6	4114	3654		
7	3170	2867		
8	4062	3579		
9	4719	4261		
10	3012	2687		
ASW(5)				
1	3582	3246		
2	3909	3572		
3	3150	2801		
4	3642	3294		
5	3561	3237	5397	4902
6	1914	1683		
7	4285	3882		
8	5397	4902		
ASW(6)				
1	2785	2320		
2	3497	3168		
3	3629	3300		
4	4178	3774		
5	4770	4191	4802	4366
6	4569	4046		
7	3755	3399		
8	4802	4366		
9	4184	3780		
ASW(7)				
1	3798	3337		

Table A.2. continued.

<i>d</i> -H binding sites	BE values (Kelvin)		Highest BE value (Kelvin)	
	-BSSE	+BSSE	-BSSE	+BSSE
2	3468	3134		
3	3525	3190		
4	3340	3005		
5	2605	2104	3798	3337
6	3560	3229		
7	3315	2967		
8	2972	2533		
ASW(8)				
1	4436	3986		
2	1633	1428		
3	2990	2586		
4	3609	3270		
5	3237	2875	4436	3986
6	3008	2686		
7	3414	3077		
8	2923	2618		
9	3642	3226		
ASW(9)				
1	2803	2492		
2	3236	2931		
3	4972	4503		
4	3132	2807		
5	5216	4761	5216	4761
6	2751	2329		
7	3560	3225		
8	1746	1518		
Total 75 sites	—	—	Average $\approx$ 4741	$\approx$ 4287

Fig. A.1. Boltzmann fitting for the 9 *d*-H positions having the highest +BSSE BE in each of the 9 ASW [H₂O]₂₀ clusters.

Table A.3. Calculated BE values for the radicals considering ASW(1) (minimum) [H₂O]₂₀ cluster.

<i>d</i> -H binding sites of ASW(1)	BE values (Kelvin)		Highest BE value (Kelvin)		Scaled by	
	-BSSE	+BSSE	-BSSE	+BSSE	1.188 for -BSSE	1.177 for +BSSE
CH radical						
1	1837	1670				
2	1688	1530				
3	1610	1454				
4	1601	1446	1892	1737	2248	2044
5	31315*	—				
6	1892	1737				
7	14746*	—				
NH radical						
1	1441	1282				
2	1409	1258				
3	1363	1223				
4	1331	1182	2083	1898	2475	2234
5	2083	1898				
6	1569	1421				
7	1425	1280				
SH radical						
1	1661	1363				
2	1870	1610				
3	1010	866				
4	1839	1572	2416	2109	2870	2482
5	2416	2109				
6	1100	942				
7	1276	1131				
CN radical						
1	1180	1068				
2	1192	1086				
3	1121	1016				
4	1028	925	1192	1086	1416	1278
5	6652*	6317*				
6	1152	1047				
7	1146	1044				
NS radical						
1	2117	1735				
2	2038	1677				
3	1808	1473				
4	2316	1879	2606	2225	3096	2619
5	2606	2225				
6	1865	1513				
7	2462	2039				
NO radical						
1	686	510				
2	540	353				
3	895	591				
4	931	598	931	598	1106	704
5	743	574				
6	658	490				
7	384	259				

Notes. * mark suggests the significantly large BE values due to the chemisorption or hemibond formation. For calculation consistency, these values are not taken into consideration.

Fig. A.2. Distribution for the overall BSSE-corrected (upper panel) and uncorrected (lower panel) BE values of the OH radicals considering all the 75 *d*-H binding sites of the 9 ASW [H₂O]₂₀ clusters.

Table A.4. BSSE-corrected (+) and uncorrected (-) BEs for OH radical considering ASW(1) [H₂O]₂₀ cluster.

<i>d</i> -H binding sites	ω B97X-D / 6-311+G(d,p)		
	-BSSE	+BSSE	$\frac{-BSSE}{+BSSE}$
1	2465	2162	1.1401
2	2955	2674	1.1051
3	1880	1500	1.1253
4	3125	2816	1.1097
5	3990	3643	1.0952
6	3116	2793	1.1156
7	1662	1452	1.1446

Fig. A.3. The optimized cluster structures are prepared using Chemcraft Version 1.8, build 682 (Zhurko 2005). Optimized structures of the chemisorbed structures of CH radical (top and middle panels) and hemibonded structure of CN radical (bottom panel) with ASW(1) $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_{20}$ cluster. Red, white, gray, and blue balls are oxygen, hydrogen, carbon, and nitrogen atoms, respectively.

Fig. A.4. Bar plots for BSSE-corrected and uncorrected BE values (upper panel) and the ratio between uncorrected and corrected BE values (lower panel) for OH radical with ASW(1) $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_{20}$ cluster.

Fig. A.5. Bar plots for scaled BSSE-corrected and uncorrected BE values with error bars for the six radical with ASW(1) [H₂O]₂₀ cluster (exceptionally large BE values are not considered for CH and CN).

References

Zhurko, G. A. 2005, ivanovo, Russia